

ASSISTIVE TECHNOLOGY FOR CHILDREN WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENT IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION SETTINGS

By

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Abstract

Visual impairment results from inability of the visual organ (eyes) to respond to visual stimuli within the environment. This poses a challenge to academic activities of children with visual impairment. This is because educational activities depend largely on the sense of vision; and 80% of learning is by vision; consequently children with visual impairment have only 20% chance to learn through other channels. But assistive technology helps children with visual impairment in various ways to meet their special learning needs by enabling them to participate optimally in academic activities and compete with sighted children in inclusive education settings. Therefore, this paper explained the concept of visual impairment, classification of children with visual impairment, concept of inclusive education, prospects of inclusive, concept of assistive technology, assistive technology devices for children with visual impairment, criteria for selecting assistive technology devices, and challenges in the use of assistive technology devices. Lastly, the paper ended with conclusion and recommendations.

Keywords: Assistive Technology, Inclusive Education, Children with Visual impairments.

Introduction

Visual impairment is a condition in which refers to defect or malfunctioning of the organ of sight. The degree of visual impairment varies from low vision to total loss of sight, i.e blindness. Children with visual impairments are those whose vision (sight) is abnormal or dysfunctional due to disease, accident, malformation, or genetics to the extent that their academic learning is affected and, consequently need assistive technology to be placed in an inclusive academic environment, and engage in teaching and learning process (Kapperman & Stricken, 2012). Assistive technology for children with visual impairments is an essential part of their inclusive educational program. The provision of assistive technology for children with visual impairment will potentially improve and enhance academic outcomes of many children with blindness and low vision in an inclusive education (Bouck & Flanagan, 2011). Inclusive education is to promote social justice, equity, equality of opportunity, and bring an end to segregation as well as stigmatization of children with special learning needs. For inclusive education to be appropriate, many things should be in place and this includes the assistive technology devices (Kapperman & Stricken, 2012).

Assistive technology in education is extremely broad. Encompassing many items, that range from pieces of equipment, products system, modified, or customized, that is used to increase, maintain, or improve functional capabilities of individual with special needs, including children with visual impairment (Lankutis & Kennedy, 2010). The assistive technology devices and applications have positive effects on the educational development of children with visual impairment. Some assistive technology devices for children with blindness, low vision or partially sighted are available in hardware or software. Typical examples are synthetic speech device which gives learners having visual impairment information through voice output; screen magnifiers, voice decoders, screen amplifiers and screen reader software, printed converters that converts printed materials into a synthetic speech; Braille sense, Braille keyboard, Braille machine, speech input and output software (Osatuyi, 2013).

Concept of Visual Impairment

Visual impairment is an umbrella term which covers all types and degrees of visual loss or deviation. A person who has low vision or partial sightedness: Myopia (Short sightedness), hyperopia (Long sightedness) astigmatism (blurred vision) or no light perception (total blindness)

or has restricted central vision or has lost sight in one eye is considered a person with visual impairment. These instances typify some form of loss or deviation or dysfunction of the visual apparatus and therefore are regarded as visual impairment (Ozaji, 2006). Besides, according to Ozaji, Unachukwu & Kolo (2016), visual impairment can be defined by two ways: legally/medically and educationally depending on the intervention given at a particular time. The Legal/medical definition describes visual impairment by considering the visual acuity of a child. Legally or medically a child is said to have visual impairment if he/she has visual acuity of 20/200 or less than that, even by using optical devices. This means that, a child with visual impairment can see an object at 20 feet whereas a sighted child can see at 200 feet. Whereas, educationally a child is said to have visual impairment if he/she cannot read ordinary print normally due to defective of the organ of vision. Such a child can only read through Braille.

Visual impairment can be congenital or adventitious. A congenital visual impairment occurs before or at birth and it is caused by a number of factors such as genetic traits, infections (like German Measles) which is transmitted from mother to the developing fetus, self-medication or taking unprescribed drugs by a pregnant woman and long labor, etc. While, adventitious visual impairment occurs sometime after birth or later in life as a result of diabetic retinopathy, glaucoma, cataract, trachoma, muscular degeneration, childhood diseases, bacterial infections, trauma or accidents, poor nutrition, injuries to the eyes, among others (Abang, 2005).

Classification of Children with Visual Impairment

In general, children with visual impairments are classified into three major groups: total blindness, low vision and partially sightedness.

A. Children with Total Blindness

Total blindness is the inability to discriminate light from dark, or the total inability to see. Total blindness is otherwise known as legal blindness with visual acuity of 20/200 or less in the better eye after the best possible correction with glasses. According to Barraga (1986) cited in Dantata & Diso (2013), Children with total blindness have complete lack of vision and No Light Perception (NLP), and must learn through Braille and related media without the use of vision.

B. Children with Partial Sightedness

Partially sighted children are those children with poor sight but whose sight is not as poor as to be regarded as blind. According to British Education Act of 1994 cited in Abang (2005), children

with partial sightedness carry out their daily activities by using their remaining vision to the fullest. Many of them suffer either myopia (near-sightedness), hyperopia (far-sightedness) or astigmatism (blurred).

C. Children with Low Vision

Barraga (1986) cited in Dantata & Diso (2013) described children with low vision as those who might have been certified blind but have some residual vision. In the past, children with visual impairment were classified into two: the blind and the partially sighted. With Barraga's findings in 1986, low vision has been included under the visual impairment. Children with low vision have visual acuity of 20/200 to 70/200 (Snellen) or 6/18 to 6/60 in the better eye after the best possible correction. Their remaining functional vision will be used depending on factors such as lighting, size of print or objects, and distance.

Concept of Inclusive Education

UNESCO (2005) cited in Andrew & Danladi (2016) defined inclusive education as responding to diverse needs of all learners by increasing participation in learning and reducing exclusion within education. This means that all children have equal right to quality education that caters for their individual needs. Inclusive education means that all children are welcomed by their neighborhood schools in age-appropriate, regular classes and are supported to learn, contribute and participate in all aspects of life in the school. Inclusive education is internationally recognized as a philosophy for attaining equity, justice and equality in education for all children, especially those who have been excluded from education for the reason of disabilities (Christopher & Elizabeth, 2012).

According to Na-ta'ala (2013), the rationale for inclusive education practice include:

- I. To provide each child or student the opportunity to learn to live and work with his/her peers in natural, integrated educational and community settings.
- II. To avoid the effects of segregation inherent when children or students are placed in separate, special schools and or classes.
- III. To do what is fair, ethical and equitable.

Prospects of Inclusive Education

Unegbu (2008) cited in Na-ta'ala (2013) outlined five prospects of inclusive education as follows:

1. Promotes a sense of co-operation and feeling of togetherness in the learner.

2. Promotion of a favourable competition among school children of different abilities, endowments, and background.
3. Presents an avenue for all utilization of the resources of all the members of the community and the teachers.
4. Provides a means of building a co-operative school community where all are accommodated and able to participate.
5. Inclusive schooling is cost effective as well as the learners are accommodated in the environment using virtually the same facilities. Unnecessary duplication of cost that are associated with segregated arrangements are avoided.

Concept of Assistive Technology

Assistive technology is as any equipment, item or product system either obtained, off the shelf, commercially or customized and used to maintain, increase or improve functional capacity for a person with special needs (Alper & Raharinirina, 2011). Assistive technology (AT) can be defined as any piece of equipment or device that may be used by a person with a needs to perform specific tasks, improve functional capabilities, and become more independent (Netherton & Deal, 2006). Assistive technology can be used in the classroom to help assist children become successful in tasks otherwise not possible. Operationally, assistive technology is defined as any equipment either acquired commercially, off the shelf, modified, or customized and utilized to enlarge, sustain, or get better useful competence for person with visual impairment (Johnston, Beard, & Carpenter, 2007).

Assistive Technology Devices for Children with Visual impairments in An Inclusive Education

A number of assistive technology devices are available for children with blindness, low vision or partially sighted which positively enable them to participate fully academic activities in an inclusive education settings. Thus, McKnight & Davies (2013) explained the assistive technology devices under two broad categories: hardware and software devices.

Hardware Devices

These are collection of all the physical components or tools developed and designed for utilization by children with visual impairment. Some of them include the following:

Talking calculator: it is a handheld device battery powered calculator that talks when being operated. It can add, multiply, subtract and divide numbers. Every key pressed by the operator will be converted into a clear human voice. It is used by children with visual impairment. Hence, see the picture of talking calculator below:

Digital voice recorder: it is a manual device that records, stores and converts sound, such as speech and other sounds into a digital file that can be used, moved from one electronic device to another, played back by a computer, tablet or Smartphone and stored like any other digital file. It is used by children with visual impairment to record their lessons, lectures and other information in the class. Hence, see the picture of digital voice recorder below:

Portable talking dictionary: it is a manual device that provides spoken pronunciations of words in addition to the normal information provided by a dictionary. In some cases, such a dictionary also speaks the definition, synonyms and other information. It is used by children with visual impairment. Hence, see the picture of talking dictionary below:

Perkins brailleur: it is a manual Brailleing device. It is sometimes calls classic writing machine used to produce Braille documents even if there is no electricity available. It is available for children with visual impairment in schools. Hence, see the picture of perkins Brailleur below:

Electric perkins braille: it is an electric Braille writing device. It can only be used when it is plugged into electricity. It enables Braille writing with much less force and for longer periods of time than manual machines. It is designed for children with blindness and those with low vision. Just like a standard Perkins Brailer, it is a portable machine. Hence, see the picture of electric perkins Brailer below:

Smart electronic Perkins Brailer: it is an electronic Braille writing device which combines a standard Braille keyboard, speech output, and Simbraille and large print on a colorful screen, creating and producing Braille documents. It can be used when it is plugged into electricity and the battery is charging or after the battery has been charged and plugged out. It is used by both children with blindness and lone vision. Hence, see the picture of smart perkins Brailer below:

Braille keyboard: it is a specialist import device that allows children with visual impairment to type and enter text or instructions for the computer in Braille. It enables children with blindness and low vision to do common tasks such as writing, browsing the internet, typing in Braille and printing in text, engaging in mail and reading documents. A Braille keyboard is connected to a computer: laptop or desktop. Hence, see the braille keyboard below:

Braille embosser: it is a device that is connected to a computer both laptops and desktop, Braille note takers, mobile devices or flash drives to generate, render and produce text or printed material into a Braille writing system. Braille Embosser is also known as Braille printer. To produce hardcopy Braille, the Braille printer has to be connected to a computer and Braille translation software must be installed to translate text into Braille code, which is then typically printed out in a Braille writing system. Braille embossers can emboss single-sided or double-sided (called interpret). Hence, see the picture of braille embosser below:

Braille note-taker (Braille Sense): it is a small portable device for the children with visual impairments. It has the same six keys as found on a Braille machine. It is primarily used to take notes in Braille. Also, the device has many powerful capacities which include the following: the users can review what they have already written, create hard copy Braille documents by connecting the unit to a Braille embosser, it has translating software which translates the Braille into normal text, print text documents using any compatible Bluetooth or USB with printer, it stores documents which can be accessed with the use of word processors, open micro soft word of documents, and read them in contracted Braille, send email messages to sighted colleagues and friends while reading incoming email messages in Braille without the need for translation, listen to music, audio books, personal recordings, or even video with the Braille sense's integrated media player, listen to and record FM radio content, etc. Hence, see the picture of braille note taker below:

Digital talking books (Hardware): These are not really things that you can hold, although they usually come on a CD-ROM today. Rather, they are files, which may also be available on the web. To put it technically, digital Talking Books are well-organized collections of computer files produced according to specifications that are published in the standards that define them. They are a medium-independent information access-and-delivery technology—the files can be stored on CD, in a directory, or on a memory card—that is based on open standards, primarily the World Wide Web Consortium’s (W3C) XML (Extensible Markup Language) and SMIL (Synchronized Multimedia Integration Language), pronounced smile.

Refreshable Braille Displays (RBD): This is a piece of computer hardware with a series of fluid braille cells on its surface to help a person with visual impairment read texts appearing on a computer screen. Most of the RBD contain a single line with a number of braille cells represented by tiny pins which can be lowered or raised to represent different Braille characters. Blind persons can run their fingers on the display to read texts on the computer screen.

A RBD, just like a computer monitor, is an output device that must be given information in order to function. This information may come from a computer running screen reader software, a smartphone, tablet or a keyboard. Most of the braille display users connect it to a computer running screen reader. Braille displays, unlike screen readers, help the user work quietly.

A RBD is a device that a screenreader user can sync with a computer, tablet, iPad, or phone that displays tactile braille characters when the screenreader user navigates the screen. It allows the blind to use mobile phones, iPhones, computers, and other smart devices. To connect a RBD, it is best to refer to the user manual that accompanies the RBD. Many have an option of either connecting via USB or via bluetooth. It is typically recommended that it must be charged

before trying to connect it as well as ensure that any necessary software/drivers are downloaded ahead of time. Hence, see the picture of refreshable braille display device below:

Magnification devices: These are technological devices that increase or enlarge the size of texts, images and graphics for children with low vision. There many magnification devices available, ranging from simple hand-held magnifying glasses to video magnifiers such as CCTVs and computer screen magnification.

- I. Hand-held magnifiers are portable and lower cost than most high-tech options. They can have a small light or can be mounted on a stand.
- II. Video magnifiers use video camera to project a magnified images onto a screen or monitor.
- III. Computer screen magnifiers. In most of the computers available today, magnification of the screens is possible by the use of special software. The user can select a portion of the screen and then enlarge that section up to 16 times of the original size. This magnification technology helps the children with low vision to see the particular portion of the screen better and larger than before. These magnification devices increase or enlarge the size of text for children with residual vision or low vision. The computer screen magnifiers can be desktop or laptop screen magnifiers.

Hence, see the picture of magnifier devices below:

Software Devices

These are set of working programs which include system software and application software developed and designed for utilization by children with visual impairment. Some of them include the following:

Window eye software (screen reader): A screen reader is a software program that enables children with visual impairment to read the text that is displayed on the computer screen with a speech synthesizer or braille display. This allows blind or low vision computer users to hear what is happening on their computer, or read it through special refreshable Braille displays. This allows children with blindness and low vision to use standard windows software, like microsoft office, internet explorer, email programmes, and so on.

A screen reader is a software application that enables people with visual impairment to use a computer. It is software that will read text out loud as a user navigates the screen, either by using keyboard or braille display commands. Screen reader works closely with the computer's Operating System (OS) to provide information about icons, menus, dialogue boxes, files and folders. The device provides access to the entire OS that it works with, including many common applications. Screen readers are available for each of the most common operating systems: Linux, Mac OS and Windows. Some of the types of screen readers include the following:

- I. JAWS (Job Access With Speech): it is for Windows Computer, desktop or laptop.
- II. Non Visual Desktop Access (NVDA): is also for Windows Computer, desktop or laptop.
- III. VoiceOver: it is for the Mac Computers, iPhones, iPads, and iPods touches.
- IV. TalkBack: it is for Android phones operating system.

Braille scanning software: OBR (Optical Braille Recognition): Optical Braille Recognition (OBR) is a Windows software program that allows to 'read' single and double sided Braille documents on a standard A4 scanner. It scans the Braille document, analyzes the dot pattern, and translates it into normal text that it presents on the computer screen.

Duxbury Braille Software: This software is a Braille translator. Translation between print and Braille is its primary function. It can translate into grade 1 (uncontracted) or grade 2 (contracted)

literary Braille for many languages, and also into several different Braille codes for mathematics and other technical notation. It can also translate from Braille into the equivalent print for several language and Braille codes. It can also provide for formatting of Braille documents, along with translation of the text. This generally implies reworking the format to a certain extent as Braille format is not always similar to print format.

Talkback Braille Keyboard: This is a software keyboard for android which enables a children with visual impairment to position their fingers on the screen and type as if they were using a Perkins Braille. It is a new virtual Braille keyboard integrated directly into android. It is a fast and convenient way for children with blindness and low vision to type on their smart phones without any additional hardware.

Text-to-Speech software: This is a type of ICT software device that reads aloud digital text- the words on computers, smart phones and tablets. All kinds of text files can be read aloud, including word and page documents. Even online web pages can be read aloud. Text-to-speech software is an assistive technology capable of reading digital text. It is also referred to as “read-aloud” technology. With a touch or a click, text-to-speech software scans text on a digital device, such as a computer or smartphone, and then turns it into speech or audio. It operates on a variety of digital devices and can read many text types, including PDF, Word, Doc and pages.

Screen magnifiers software: it is software application that increase the size of text and graphics on your computer screen. When installed on a computer, tablet or smartphone, it enlarge everything for easy reading by children with low vision or partially sighted. It helps children with residual vision to access and interact with digital content such as websites or documents.

Digital Accessible Information System (DAISY): it is a technical standard for digital audiobooks, periodicals, and computerized text. DAISY is designed to be a complete audio substitute for print material and is specifically designed for use by persons with "print use limitation", including children blindness, low vision, and partial sightedness. Based on the MP3 and XML formats, the DAISY format has advanced features in addition to those of a traditional audio book. Users can search, place bookmarks, precisely navigate line by line, and regulate the

speaking speed without distortion. DAISY also provides aurally accessible tables, references, and additional information. As a result, DAISY allows visually impaired listeners to navigate something as complex as an encyclopedia or textbook, otherwise impossible using conventional audio recordings.

DAISY multimedia can be a book, magazine, newspaper, journal, computerized text, or a synchronized presentation of text and audio. It provides up to six embedded "navigation levels" for content, including embedded objects such as images, graphics, and Math. In the DAISY standard, navigation is enabled within a sequential and hierarchical structure consisting of (marked-up) text synchronized with audio.

Digital Talking Book players (Software)/ Downloadable Audio Books: These books are digital files that contain the same content as conventional audio books but can be downloaded onto a personal computer or a portable device such as an MP3 player. Apps for the iPhone, iPad or iPod Touch make the download and listening process seamless for many audio books. If you are not technically oriented, the digital option may seem unfamiliar, but it does have advantages that make it worth exploring. The main advantage is navigation. CDs offer limited movement backward or forward within the text. Digital playback is much more flexible, allowing the user to jump back or

forward by chapter or sometimes by page. You can even set digital bookmarks that let you find a particular passage instantly. Here is more information about downloadable audio books:

1. Electronic Audio Books are recorded electronically and stored in files on the Web, or downloaded to your own computer.
2. Sometimes they are especially designed for people who are blind or have low vision and use the DAISY (Digital Accessible Information SYstem) format.
3. This format has encoded markers for chapters, subheadings, paragraphs, and other codes that help the listener navigate through the book and bookmark passages of interest.
4. The DAISY format means that Digital Audio Books will not work on players that are not designed to play them.
5. If you have a computer, you can get software that can play the DAISY format. You can also buy a stand-alone machine that plays Digital Audio Books.
6. Some Personal Digital Assistants (PDAs) can play the DAISY format. Look for a PDA that understands DAISY and has sufficient memory for storing your books.
7. Stand-alone machines can also be small and portable and will play MP3 files and music CDs too.
8. DAISY books can contain both text and audio files. The text portion can be displayed on a braille display or on a screen in a larger font size. You can search the text for key words or passages. Unlike CDs, you don't have to rewind or fast forward. And you can increase or decrease the reading speed without affecting the quality of the narrator's voice. Ask yourself the following questions before purchasing a digital audio book player.
 - Do you want a portable player or a software player that runs on your computer? If you want to use it on your computer, you will need a software player that is compatible with your computer's operating system.
 - If you have a portable player, does your PDA already support the DAISY format and have sufficient memory for storing books? Can your PDA memory be expanded?
 - Do you want a player that plays CDs, or a player that plays files transferred directly from your computer? Should it also play MP3, WAV, WMA file formats?
 - If you are buying software, do you want a version that allows you to produce, as well as listen to, books?

Criteria for Selecting of Assistive Technology Devices

Prior to selecting or purchasing of assistive technology devices for any children with visual impairment, it should be evaluated in order to acquire the optimum functionality. The criteria used to select assistive technology devices are:

Effectiveness: How much the device improve the user’s living situation and enhances functional capability and independence.

Affordability: The extent to which a person can purchase, maintain, and repair a device without financial hardship.

Reliability: The degree to which a device is dependable, consistent and predictable in its performance and levels of accuracy for reasonable amount of time.

Portability: The device’s size and weight on the user’s ability to move, carry, relocate and operate it in varied locations.

Durability: The extent to which a device delivers continued operation for an extended period of time.

Securability: How well a consumer believes that a device affords physical control and is secure from theft or vandalism

Safety: How well a device protects the user, care provider or family member from potential harm, bodily injury or infection.

Learnability: The device's ease of assembly, initial learning requirements and time & effort to master use.

Comfort & Acceptance: The extent to which a user feels physically comfortable with the device and doesn't experience pain or discomfort with use; how aesthetically appealing the user finds the device and the user's psychological comfort when using it in private or public.

Maintenance & Reparability: The degree to which the device is easy to maintain and repair (either by the consumer, a local repair shop or a supplier).

Operability: The extent to which the device is easy to use, is adaptable and flexible, and affords easy access to controls and displays.

Challenges of Using Assistive Technologies

1. Lack of knowledge on how to use assistive technologies.
2. Limited ICT infrastructure
3. Shortage/limited number of Assistive Technology tools
4. Absence of experts or technical assistance
5. Most assistive technology devices are not customized to suite our environment.
Lack of culture of maintenance of Assistive technology tools
6. High cost associated to some assistive technology tools
7. Technophobia (Phobia of technology).

Conclusion

Inclusive education is essentially a programme that enables all learners with different abilities and diverse needs to participate fully in the academic activities of regular school. It gives equal opportunity for all learners to jointly undertake learning situations without discrimination and any learner considered to have a deviation as a result of a lost or defect in physical and mental development is given the right to belong to the inclusive setting. The understanding is that children with special needs do not only have the right to education, they also have the right to be part of the inclusive education system. For this reason, children with blindness, low vision or partially sighted have it as a right to be in an inclusive classroom setting for teaching and learning process. Therefore, it is concluded that for children with visual impairment to maximally benefit from inclusive education programmes, there is need for the provision of assistive technology devices. Some assistive technology devices that enhance and promote inclusive education of children with visual impairments include: talking dictionary, digital voice recorder, talking calculator, Braille machine, computer with speech synthesizer software (JAWS), magnification devices, among others.

Recommendations

1. Assistive technology devices should be adequately provided by government and other agencies or NGOs.
2. Assistive technology devices should be available and accessible by children with visual impairment.
3. Assistive technology devices should be affordable by children with visual impairment.
4. Assistive technology devices should be easily adapted by children with visual impairment.
5. Effective monitoring, periodic review and regular maintenance of assistive technology devices are needed for successful implementation of inclusive education system for children with blindness, low vision or partially sighted.

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